

1 Article

2 A Copernicus Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 classification 3 framework for the 2020+ European Common 4 Agricultural Policy: A case study in València (Spain)

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11 **Abstract:** This paper proposes a methodology for deriving an agreement map between the Spanish
12 Land Parcel Information System (LPIS), also known as SIGPAC, and a classification map obtained
13 from multitemporal Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data. **The study area compresses the province of**
14 **València (Spain).** The approach exploits predictions and class probabilities obtained from an
15 ensemble method of decision trees (boosting trees). The overall accuracy reaches 91.18% when using
16 only Sentinel-2 data and increases up to 93.96% when Sentinel-1 data are added in the training
17 process. Blending both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data causes a remarkable classification
18 improvement ranging from 3.6 to 8.7 percentage points over shrubs, forest, and pasture with trees,
19 which are the most confusing classes in the optical domain as demonstrated by a spectral
20 separability analysis. The derived agreement map is built upon combining per pixel classifications,
21 their probabilities, and the Spanish LPIS. This map can be exploited into the decision making chain
22 for subsidies payment to cope with the 2020+ European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

23 **Keywords:** Sentinel-1; Sentinel-2; Classification; Ensemble of boosting decision trees; Common
24 Agricultural Policy (CAP)

25

26 1. Introduction

27 The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is one of the most major European Commission (EC)
28 policies. With a budget of €385 billion [1] (28.5% of the overall European budget in the period 2021–
29 2027), the CAP provides support to European farmers with the aim of ensuring the provision of
30 affordable food also guarantying its quality on European markets. In this context, €65.2 billion (68.9%
31 of the total CAP budget) is for direct payments. CAP requirements for payments are bound to the
32 agricultural land cover and land use. **Every** member state authorities must verify farmers'
33 declarations in order to comply with legal cross-compliance control mechanisms [2]. If farmers'
34 declarations do not fit the CAP requirements and standards, associated payments could be canceled.
35 Paying agencies of every member state are responsible of supervising at least 5% of the received
36 declarations. **This is achieved** by means of *in situ* field inspections and photo-interpretation of very
37 high-resolution images acquired from airborne or satellite platforms. Field inspections are expensive
38 mainly when large areas have to be assessed. **In addition**, the photo-interpretation is a time-
39 consuming task, which may lead to different results depending on both inspector visual skills and
40 the quality of the images. The EC adopted on 22 May 2018 a new regulation for 2020+ CAP payments
41 that include the possibility of using Earth Observation (EO) data from the Copernicus Sentinel-1 and
42 Sentinel-2 programs for monitoring farmers' parcels and assess cross-compliance [3]. This action will

43 be applied to all declarations whereas only 5% of the declarations concerned by eligibility criteria,
44 commitments and other obligations that cannot be monitored by EO data, will be supervised carrying
45 out *in situ* checks. This oncoming regulation also attempts to alleviate the administrative red tape in
46 order to facilitate the interaction between farmers and paying agencies.

47 Some of the most widely used remote sensing (cost-free) data in land cover and land use studies
48 are provided by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) (e.g., MODIS data) [4],
49 and the United States Geological Survey (USGS) (e.g., Landsat data) [5,6]). They deliver spectral
50 information of land surface at global coverage with a per pixel spatial resolutions ranging from 250
51 m – 1 km, in the case of MODIS, to 30 m in the case of Landsat. Temporal resolution varies from 16
52 days for Landsat to 1-16 days for MODIS (depending on the temporal composite period of the
53 product). These features make them suitable for classification and vegetation monitoring over large
54 areas. However, this spatial resolution can be a limitation for classification mainly over very
55 heterogeneous areas **characterized by** small landholdings. In the frame of the **European Space**
56 **Agency (ESA)** Copernicus program, data from the Sentinel-1 [7] and Sentinel-2 [8] are freely
57 disseminated. These data provide global information at decametric spatial resolution every 5-6 days,
58 offering promising possibilities for land use classification. As a result, several classification studies
59 have recently sprung up in the literature with the aim of classifying crop types, tree species, and
60 grassland habitats [9-13].

61 In general, crop classification approaches can be faced at pixel level or at parcel level (i.e, object-
62 based) depending on both the spatial resolution of available images and the characteristics of the
63 target area. In object-based approaches, the unit to be classified is the so-called object, which is built
64 up from the image segmentation whereas in pixel-based approaches pixels are classified individually
65 without taking into account spatial aggregation. Irrespective of the classification unit, EO techniques
66 for deriving classification maps are usually based on supervised learning. Among the most widely
67 used supervised classification algorithms we can find decision trees (DT) [14], k-nearest neighbor (k-
68 NN) [15], support vector machines (SVM) [16], and random forests (RF) [17]. SVM and RF usually
69 trend to outperform DT and k-NN [18-20]. In addition, we can find the literature several studies
70 combining classifiers and multitemporal remote sensing data [21,22] leading to higher accuracies in
71 the classification.

72 Although many studies have been undertaken on automatic vegetation classification from
73 remote sensing data, to date of writing, only few of them are addressed and set up to cope with the
74 context of European CAP subsidies [23-26]. However, none of them deals with the need of updating
75 the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS), which is key for both improving LPIS reliability and
76 distribution of CAP payments also reducing administrative costs [27]. In this context, this paper
77 describes a classification framework from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 developed for improving
78 subsidies control for the CAP in the Valencian Community (Spain) also assessing the LPIS update.
79 The classification exploits time series of both optical and microwave data, vegetation indices (VIs), as
80 well as features provided by assembling decision trees. The main novelties include two folds. First,
81 in this paper we benefit from full capabilities of ensemble classifiers' outputs using not only class
82 predictions but also the class probability obtained from the ensemble of decision trees which is not
83 very often exploited in most of remote sensing classification studies. Second, we combine both the
84 prediction and its probability with the Spanish LPIS to derive an agreement map between derived
85 classification and Spanish LPIS. This achievement **demonstrates** its applicability for decision making
86 in the framework of CAP subsidies.

87 2. Data collection

88 2.1. Study area

89 The study area selected in this work belongs to the land portion of an entire Sentinel-2 tile
90 covering part of the Valencian Community (see red square in Figure 1). The Sentinel-2 tile is the
91 T30SYJ embracing 110 km × 110 km. The selected study area falls within a Sentinel-1 tile in descending
92 mode that allows the combination of both source of information. The study area is located over the

93 Valencia province (East of Spain) having a typical Mediterranean climate, with an average annual
 94 temperature and humidity of 17 °C and 65%, respectively. The dominant non-urban classes over the
 95 study area are shrubs (SH), fruits (FR), citrus (CI), forest (FO), rice crops (RI), olive grove (OL),
 96 pasture with trees (PAT), vineyards (VI), dried fruit (DFR), and pasture (PA), which altogether cover
 97 the majority of the study area.

98

99 **Figure 1.** Location of the study area in the Valencian Community (blue shape), East of Spain, and the
 100 corresponding Sentinel-1 (green) and Sentinel-2 (red) tiles.

101 2.2. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data

102 ESA provides open access to Copernicus Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data from the Sentinels
 103 Scientific Data Hub (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>). In this study we used the **Sentinel-1** Level-1
 104 Ground Range Detected (GRD) product that uses the **Wide swath (IW)** mode providing data in VV
 105 and VH polarizations. The data were calibrated to compute backscatter coefficient (sigma nought, σ^0)
 106 , and subsequently a **multilooking** was applied in order to mitigate the speckle noise effect with
 107 a 2×2 window size. Eventually, in order to correct geometric distortions caused by slant range,
 108 layover, shadows and foreshortening, a geometric correction was performed using the digital
 109 elevation model from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission at 1" resolution (SRTM, 1sec Grid).
 110 These processing were undertaken using the Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP).

111 **Sentinel-2 top-of-atmosphere reflectances (Level 1C) were downloaded and atmospherically**
 112 **corrected using the Sen2Cor (Sentinel-2 atmospheric Correction) toolbox [28] to obtain top-of-**
 113 **canopy corrected reflectance for all bands excluding the B10 band (cirrus band), which does not**
 114 **contain surface information over the study area.**

115 Sentinel-2 Level 1C data were downloaded jointly with the Sentinel-1 GRD data from April 2017
 116 to March 2018 embracing 30 Sentinel-1 and 11 Sentinel-2 images for the study area (see **Table 1**). Only
 117 completely cloud-free Sentinel-2 images were considered throughout the temporal window from
 118 April 2017 to March 2018, which was selected to account for a complete vegetation cycle of all classes
 119 within the study area.

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Table 1. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 acquisition dates in 2017 and 2018.

	2017	2018
Sentinel-1	April 12th, April 24th May 6th, May 18th, May 30th June 5th, June 17th, June 29th July 11th, July 23th August 4th, August 16th, August 28th September 9th, September 21st October 3th, October 15th, October 27th November 8th, November 20th December 2nd, December 14th, December 26th	January 7th, January 31th, January 19th February 12th, February 24th, March 20th, March 8th
Sentinel-2	May 6th, May 26th June 15th September 13th October 13th December 2nd, December 17th	January 21st, May 26th February 15th March 7th, March 27th

122 2.3. SIGPAC

123 Several European countries, including Spain, have got their own Land Parcel Identification
 124 System (LPIS) that is annually updated [23-25]. In Spain the LPIS is given by the Sistema de
 125 Información Geográfica de Parcelas Agrícolas (SIGPAC), which assigns to every agricultural parcel
 126 a unique land use (SIGPAC use). **SIGPAC allows the geographic identification of parcels declared
 127 by farmers and livestock farmers, under any subsidy regime relating to the area which is cultivated
 128 or used for livestock. It was built upon an orthophotography mosaic embracing the Spanish
 129 territory, in which cadastral information collected by authorities is overimposed
 130 (<https://www.fega.es>).**

131 SIGPAC classifies the uses into categories including natural vegetation, urban zones and mixed
 132 classes. In this study we have selected the main 10 classes that cover the vast majority of agricultural
 133 parcels over the study area (listed in Section 2.1 and Section 2.3). We have excluded urban areas and
 134 buildings, mixed classes, water bodies and very-low representative classes. Figure 2 shows the
 135 considered SIGPAC classes over the study area in 2017, **and the percentage coverage of every class.**
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(a)

(b)

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Figure 2. (a) SIGPAC over the study area. Mediterranean Sea and classes of non-interest are masked out. (b) Coverage of every class over the area.

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145 2.4. Ground truth

146 The Valencian regional government, specifically its Department of Agriculture, Environment,
 147 Climate Change, and Rural Development (<http://www.agroambient.gva.es/va/>), provided us with an
 148 extensive ground truth regarding SIGPAC classes (see Table 1). It was obtained through several field
 149 campaigns and parcel inspections as well as thanks to the expert knowledge provided by regional
 150 authorities' technical agronomists.

151 **Table 1.** Ground truth: Number of pixels for every class.

Class	Shrubs	Dried fruit	Fruits	Pasture	Rice	Forest	Vineyard	Pasture with trees	Olive groove	Citrus
No. Pixels	20382	20703	19800	20058	20157	20478	20295	18846	19434	20385

152 3. Methodology

153 The methodology is outlined in Figure 3 which includes the main following steps: (i) data
 154 collection of ground truth, and processing selected Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 images as described in
 155 Section 2.2, (ii) feature selection and spectral separability analysis, (iii) assessment of different
 156 classifiers accuracy over a test set never used during the training process, (iv) selection of the best
 157 classification method and derivation of both a classification and a class probability map over the
 158 study area (masking out the sea and non-interest areas), and (v) generation of an agreement map
 159 between the derived classification map and SIGPAC.

160 **Figure 3.** Schema of the followed methodology for the derivation of the proposed agreement map.
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162 3.1. Feature selection

163 Although the downloaded Sentinel-2 images are cloud free, it may occur that the atmospheric
 164 correction provided artifacts or slight changes in reflectance over the same classes in different dates
 165 (changes not related to vegetation phenology), which would introduce noise in the training process
 166 leading to worse classification results. To avoid non-optimal Sentinel-2 images, **as well as to alleviate**
 167 **the Hughes phenomenon [29] related with the decrease of the classification performance as**
 168 **increasing the number of features**, a Sentinel-2 image selection was made using the Jeffries–Matusita
 169 (JM) [30] and Bhattacharyya (BH) [31] distances. The JM distance is a measure of the average distance
 170 between a pair of two classes defined as

171
$$J_{ij} = 2(1 - e^{-B_{ij}}),$$

172 where B_{ij} is the Bhattacharyya distance given by:

173
$$B_{ij} = \frac{1}{8} (\mu_i - \mu_j)^t \left[\frac{\Sigma_i + \Sigma_j}{2} \right]^{-1} (\mu_i - \mu_j)^t + \frac{1}{2} \ln \left[\frac{|\Sigma_i + \Sigma_j|/2}{\sqrt{|\Sigma_i||\Sigma_j|}} \right]$$

174 Being μ_i and μ_j the mean vectors of the two considered classes and Σ_i and Σ_j the corresponding
 175 covariance matrices. The JM distance ranges from 0 to 2 as increasing separability between classes,
 176 whereas a B_{ij} larger value corresponds to higher average distance between classes. In the case of
 177 having normally distributed classes, J_{ij} becomes B_{ij} [30].

178 In addition to the selected Sentinel-2 images, a set of VIs (see Table 3) were stacked to the
 179 Sentinel-2 images feature space (i.e., used as predictors during the training). In particular, we
 180 considered the wide-used Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) [32] and its red-edge
 181 version (NDVI₇₀₅) [33], the Modified Chlorophyll Absorption in Reflectance Index (MCARI) [34]
 182 which accounts for chlorophyll changes, the Plant Senescence Reflectance Index (PSRI) [35] that is
 183 sensitive to plant senescence, and in order to minimize soil background noise, both the Optimized
 184 Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (OSAVI) [36] and its red-edge version (OSAVI₇₀₅).

185 **Table 3.** Vegetation indices used in the feature space. Reflectance is denoted by ρ_λ (λ in nm).

Vegetation Index	Equation
NDVI	$\frac{\rho_{842} - \rho_{665}}{\rho_{842} + \rho_{665}}$
OSAVI	$\frac{\rho_{842} - \rho_{665}}{\rho_{842} + \rho_{665} + 0.16}$
NDVI ₇₀₅	$\frac{\rho_{842} - \rho_{705}}{\rho_{842} + \rho_{705}}$
OSAVI ₇₀₅	$\frac{\rho_{842} - \rho_{705}}{\rho_{842} + \rho_{705} + 0.16}$
MCARI	$[(\rho_{705} - \rho_{665}) - 0.2(\rho_{705} - \rho_{560})] \left(\frac{\rho_{705}}{\rho_{665}} \right)$
PSRI	$\frac{\rho_{665} - \rho_{560}}{\rho_{740}}$

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187 The selected Sentinel-2 images and VIs, were jointly stacked with the available Sentinel-1 images
 188 to build the remote sensing data set (see Figure 4) used for the classification. Hence, the final training
 189 feature space was formed by both optical and SAR data. From the microwave domain the VV and
 190 VH polarizations were used, as well as the VH/VV ratio, which is employed in crop classification for
 191 being considered as a good indicator of vegetation status [10, 37]. In addition, to assess the impact of
 192 Sentinel-1 in the classification, an experiment was undertaken by removing Sentinel-1 data to the six
 193 selected Sentinel-2 images and VIs. In this case, the training feature space was formed only by optical
 194 data.

195 3.2. Classifiers

196 The ground truth was associated to the remote sensing data, and was then split into two sets,
 197 training and test set, comprising 2/3 and 1/3 of the pixels, respectively. The big effort made by the
 198 Valencian authorities allowed us to build a huge training set with balanced classes avoiding thus
 199 issues introduced by imbalanced training samples [12].

200 Several classification algorithms based on supervised classification were trained using the
 201 training set, and their respective accuracies were assessed over the test set (see results in Section 4.2).
 202 For instance, a linear discriminant analysis (LDA), which is a classification algorithm based on a
 203 linear transformation of variables that reduces an original feature space to a lower one that maximizes
 204 separability among class distributions [38]. In addition, non-linear approaches such as the quadratic
 205 discriminant analysis (QDA) and the k-NN classifier have been considered. The k-NN algorithm is
 206 based on neighbor similarity features where the prediction is done taking into account the k-nearest
 207 neighbors, where k is a real number typically ranging from 1 to a given number depending on image
 208 spatial features. We also considered the use of SVM which is a kernel method (i.e., a method that
 209 samples input data into a Hilbert space) that divides the training data using hyperplanes maximizing
 210 the margin [16].

211 Finally, for having a more comprehensive sense, we decided to use ensembles of classifiers based
 212 on decision trees. For the ensemble, different techniques such as bagging, boosting and, random
 213 forest [39] were used. In the bagging ensemble, every decision tree is trained on a random subset of
 214 training samples. The same sample can be selected for training all, several, or even none of the

215 decision trees composing the ensemble. In the case of RF the approach is similar to bagging, the
 216 difference relies in the split of the nodes of every tree. The bagging method uses all input features for
 217 splitting the nodes whereas in the RF approach the split is done considering a number of features
 218 (typically its square root), which are selected randomly. In the boosting method, trees are trained
 219 using all training samples in an iterative approach that increases the weights for samples classified
 220 incorrectly in previous training rounds. The boosting approach uses multiple iterations to generate a
 221 single composite strong learner. In this study, the *Adaboost.M2* algorithm [40] was used for boosting
 222 decision trees. The algorithm takes a bootstrap sample in every boosting iteration that is used for
 223 building a weak classifier. Then the pseudo-loss is computed and used for updating the sampling
 224 weights to be used for the next iteration. The final assignation for every pixel is given by the most
 225 frequent class, obtained from all decision trees in the ensemble.

226 3.3. Agreement map

227 An agreement map between the classification map derived from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, and
 228 SIGPAC was calculated. For this purpose, a series of logical rules have been proposed in order to
 229 discriminate eight levels of agreement. The levels of agreement were obtained blending the
 230 information provided by SIGPAC, and both the derived classification and confidence maps as
 231 described in Table 4.

232 **Table 4.** Agreement levels between classifications and SIGPAC.

Classification map and SIGPAC		Classification confidence	Level of agreement
Same class	AND	> 95%	Very high agreement
Same class	AND	70% – 95%	High agreement
Same class	AND	50% – 70%	Significant agreement
Same class	AND	< 50%	Low agreement
Different classes	AND	< 50%	Low discrepancy
Different classes	AND	50% – 70%	Significant discrepancy
Different classes	AND	50% – 70%	High discrepancy
Different classes	AND	> 95%	Very high discrepancy

233 4. Results and analysis

234 4.1. Sentinel-2 spectral separability analysis

235 Sentinel-2 image selection was made using the aforementioned JM and BH distances over the
 236 optical domain (i.e., Sentinel-2 bands). Only the images that maximize the class separability were
 237 used, which led to the choice of 6 out of 11 available and cloud free Sentinel-2 images. Table 5 shows
 238 the JM (upper diagonal) and BH (lower diagonal) distances obtained for the first selected Sentinel-2
 239 image, which was acquired on May 6th, 2017 over the study area (for the sake of brevity, we show
 240 the rest of JM/BH tables in Supplementary Material (Tables S1-S5)). It can be observed that several
 241 classes reach JM values close to 2, which highlights the good separability between pair of classes. It
 242 is worth mentioning rice is the most distinguishable class, exhibiting JM values very close to 2 and
 243 the highest BH values. On the other hand, forest, pasture with trees, and shrubs are the classes
 244 presenting lowest JM and BH values among them (<0.5), which denotes their respective significant
 245 spectral confusion being thus more difficult to classify, a priori. Similarly, fruits and olive grove are
 246 also classes with short distances between them and difficult to discriminate. In addition, the JM and
 247 BH distances were computed taking into account all six selected Sentinel-2 images jointly (see Table
 248 6). In this case, the results are better than the ones obtained individually for every of the six selected
 249 Sentinel-2 images, which evince the use of multitemporal features improves spectral separability
 250 among classes. However, for forest, pasture with trees, and shrubs, although their spectral
 251 separability increase, remain the lowest.

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254 **Table 5.** Jeffries–Matusita (JM) and Bhattacharyya (BH) distances for Sentinel-2 image acquired on
 255 May 6th, 2017. **Classes:** shrubs (SH), fruits (FR), citrus (CI), forest (FO), rice crops (RI), olive grove
 256 (OL), pasture with trees (PAT), vineyards (VI), dried fruit (DFR), and pasture (PA).

BH \ JM	SH	DFR	FR	PA	RI	FO	VI	PAT	OL	CI
SH		1.750	1.597	1.508	1.996	0.636	1.870	0.253	1.497	1.879
DFR	2.078		0.392	0.698	1.983	1.863	0.466	1.717	0.402	1.439
FR	1.603	0.218		0.621	1.985	1.760	0.672	1.538	0.250	1.472
PA	1.403	0.429	0.371		1.986	1.653	1.202	1.410	0.505	1.123
RI	6.102	4.776	4.880	4.939		1.989	1.989	1.986	1.988	1.995
FO	0.382	2.679	2.120	1.752	5.228		1.951	0.296	1.713	1.899
VI	2.731	0.265	0.409	0.919	5.249	3.714		1.872	0.792	1.692
PAT	0.135	1.955	1.465	1.221	4.991	0.160	2.752		1.446	1.837
OL	1.381	0.225	0.133	0.291	5.135	1.942	0.504	1.283		1.382
CI	2.802	1.271	1.331	0.825	6.033	2.988	1.870	2.509	1.174	

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258 **Table 6.** Jeffries–Matusita (JM) and Bhattacharyya (BH) distances taking into account all the six
 259 selected Sentinel-2 images. **Classes:** shrubs (SH), fruits (FR), citrus (CI), forest (FO), rice crops (RI),
 260 olive grove (OL), pasture with trees (PAT), vineyards (VI), dried fruit (DFR), and pasture (PA).

BH \ JM	SH	DFR	FR	PA	RI	FO	VI	PAT	OL	CI
SH		1.750	1.597	1.508	1.996	0.636	1.870	0.253	1.497	1.879
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FR	1.603	0.218		0.621	1.985	1.760	0.672	1.538	0.250	1.472
PA	1.403	0.429	0.371		1.986	1.653	1.202	1.410	0.505	1.123
RI	6.102	4.776	4.880	4.939		1.989	1.989	1.986	1.988	1.995
FO	0.382	2.679	2.120	1.752	5.228		1.951	0.296	1.713	1.899
VI	2.731	0.265	0.409	0.919	5.249	3.714		1.872	0.792	1.692
PAT	0.135	1.955	1.465	1.221	4.991	0.160	2.752		1.446	1.837
OL	1.381	0.225	0.133	0.291	5.135	1.942	0.504	1.283		1.382
CI	2.802	1.271	1.331	0.825	6.033	2.988	1.870	2.509	1.174	

261 4.2. Accuracy assessment

262 Different classifiers were trained using the training set and their respective accuracies were
 263 assessed over the test set (constituted by one third of the pixels never used during the training). Table
 264 7 shows the overall accuracy (OA) and kappa index (κ) [41] of the results taking into account the
 265 different features used in the classifications, i.e., if any vegetation index was stacked to Sentinel-1 and
 266 Sentinel-2 data. Among all evaluated classifiers and vegetation indices, the ensembles of decision
 267 trees revealed the highest accuracies being the boosting approach the most accurate using the
 268 temporal information of OSAVI₇₀₅. It is interesting to highlight that the boosting approach
 269 outperforms not only the rest of ensemble approaches but also the rest of classifiers irrespective of
 270 the VI. If no VI is used in addition to the selected images, the classification performance is reduced
 271 (i.e., OA=88.19% and κ =0.87 obtained without VIs vs OA=93.96% and κ =0.91 obtained in the best case).
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275**Table 7.** Overall accuracy (OA) and kappa index (κ) obtained in the test set for every classifier. Best result highlighted in bold.

Multitemporal features (Optical + SAR)	Overall Accuracy (%) (κ)						
	LDA	QDA	k-NN	SVM	RF	Bagging trees	Boosting trees
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + NDVI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	69.82 (0.68)	80.36 (0.79)	84.93 (0.83)	86.80 (0.85)	88.69 (0.87)	88.30 (0.87)	92.66 (0.90)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + OSAVI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	70.58 (0.69)	80.45 (0.79)	85.68 (0.84)	86.97 (0.85)	88.86 (0.87)	88.48 (0.87)	93.58 (0.91)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + NDVI ₇₀₅ 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	67.54 (0.66)	76.41 (0.75)	83.29 (0.82)	85.29 (0.84)	87.64 (0.86)	87.23 (0.86)	90.75 (0.89)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + OSAVI ₇₀₅ 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	70.95 (0.70)	80.50 (0.79)	85.94 (0.85)	86.99 (0.84)	89.05 (0.88)	88.76 (0.87)	93.96 (0.91)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + MCARI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	68.93 (0.68)	77.83 (0.76)	83.15 (0.82)	85.04 (0.84)	88.15 (0.87)	87.51 (0.86)	90.15 (0.89)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + PSRI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	66.94 (0.66)	71.60 (0.69)	76.83 (0.75)	84.07 (0.83)	87.10 (0.86)	87.08 (0.86)	88.96 (0.88)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	66.73 (0.65)	70.23 (0.69)	75.84 (0.74)	85.59 (0.84)	86.80 (0.85)	86.25 (0.85)	88.19 (0.87)

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Table 8 shows the corresponding confusion matrix (i.e., for the best result in Table 6). In general, the results are good, and the majority of classes reveal both user's accuracy (UA) and producer's accuracy (PA) higher than 90% and 94%, respectively. However, shrubs, forest and pasture with trees presented lower accuracies ranging 82% – 88% with confusion among them. It is worth mentioning that this behavior is in accordance with the a priori analysis carried out using the JM and BH distances. The best result is obtained over rice where both UA and PA reach 99.9%, whereas pasture with trees is the class with worst UA (82%), and shrubs is the class with worst PA (81.8%).

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Table 8. Confusion matrix of the classification obtained for the boosting approach using as predictors Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery, and OSAVI₇₀₅. **Classes: shrubs (SH), fruits (FR), citrus (CI), forest (FO), rice crops (RI), olive grove (OL), pasture with trees (PAT), vineyards (VI), dried fruit (DFR), and pasture (PA).**

		Ground truth										Total	UA (%)
		SH	DFR	FR	PA	RI	FO	VI	PAT	OL	CI		
Classified	SH	5560	19	19	1	0	259	1	329	69	7	6264	88.8
	DFR	24	6619	10	1	0	7	5	12	72	12	6762	97.9
	FR	70	63	6450	4	1	36	20	36	87	16	6783	95.1
	PA	3	8	1	6661	0	3	2	1	10	3	6692	99.5
	RI	1	1	0	2	6717	1	0	1	1	0	6724	99.9
	FO	455	11	15	5	0	5845	1	349	38	12	6731	86.8
	VI	3	11	18	1	0	0	6719	1	35	3	6791	98.9
	PAT	500	36	27	2	1	569	0	5443	50	10	6638	82.0
	OL	175	118	53	7	0	105	14	104	6101	36	6713	90.9
	CI	3	15	7	2	0	1	3	6	15	6696	6748	99.2
	Total	6794	6901	6600	6686	6719	6826	6765	6282	6478	6795	OA=93.96%	
PA (%)	81.8	95.9	97.7	99.6	99.9	85.6	99.3	86.6	94.2	98.5	$\kappa=0.91$		

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As highlighted by the aforementioned results, the family of ensemble of trees provided the highest accuracies. The sensitivity of the ensembles of decision trees to the number of trees was analyzed by executing different ensembles with increasing number of trees (see Figure 4). OA was calculated from 1 to 100 trees in steps of 10, and from 100 to 1000 in steps of 100. Results show that 1000 decision trees are sufficient for obtaining stable and accurate predictions. Belgiu & Drăguț [42] suggested that 500 trees are acceptable for remote sensing studies, however other studies use a number of trees ranging from 10 up to 5000 depending on the number of features and spectral-temporal features of the remote sensing data used [43, 44].

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Figure 4. Influence of number of trees on the overall accuracy of the ensemble of decision trees.

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We also assessed the effect of removing Sentinel-1 data in the classification. In this case, the training feature space was formed only by optical data. The removing of Sentinel-1 images (microwave data) worsen classification accuracies in all cases (see Table 9) compared to the respective results in Table 7. In this case, the best results were obtained when fusing the selected six Sentinel-2 multispectral images and the OSAVI₇₀₅. Again, the boosting approach outperforms the rest of classifiers (OA=91.18% and $\kappa=0.88$). Table 10 shows the confusion matrix over the test set obtained in this case. The results are not so accurate than the previous case when using both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data (see Table 8) revealing a general decrease in accuracy for every class. It is worth mentioning that in terms of percentage points (pp) in UA this loss is greater over shrubs (5.5 pp), forest (8.7 pp), and pasture with trees (3.6 pp), and in PA the loss is 7.5 pp for shrubs, 5.6 pp for forest, and 4.5 pp for pasture with trees. In addition, the confusion among these classes was also increased.

311 This confirms that the combined use of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 is useful for improving classification
 312 results.

313 **Table 9.** Overall accuracy (OA) and kappa index (κ) obtained in the test set for every classifier using
 314 as predictors only Sentinel-2 data and VIs. Best result highlighted in bold.

Multitemporal features (Optical + SAR)	Overall Accuracy (%) (κ)						
	LDA	QDA	k-NN	SVM	RF	Bagging trees	Boosting trees
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + NDVI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	69.82 (0.68)	80.36 (0.79)	84.93 (0.83)	86.80 (0.85)	88.69 (0.87)	88.30 (0.87)	92.66 (0.90)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + OSAVI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	70.58 (0.69)	80.45 (0.79)	85.68 (0.84)	86.97 (0.85)	88.86 (0.87)	88.48 (0.87)	93.58 (0.91)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + NDVI ₇₀₅ 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	67.54 (0.66)	76.41 (0.75)	83.29 (0.82)	85.29 (0.84)	87.64 (0.86)	87.23 (0.86)	90.75 (0.89)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + OSAVI ₇₀₅ 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	70.95 (0.70)	80.50 (0.79)	85.94 (0.85)	86.99 (0.84)	89.05 (0.88)	88.76 (0.87)	93.96 (0.91)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + MCARI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	68.93 (0.68)	77.83 (0.76)	83.15 (0.82)	85.04 (0.84)	88.15 (0.87)	87.51 (0.86)	90.15 (0.89)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) + PSRI 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	66.94 (0.66)	71.60 (0.69)	76.83 (0.75)	84.07 (0.83)	87.10 (0.86)	87.08 (0.86)	88.96 (0.88)
6 × Sentinel-2 (12 bands) 30 × Sentinel-1 (3 bands)	66.73 (0.65)	70.23 (0.69)	75.84 (0.74)	85.59 (0.84)	86.80 (0.85)	86.25 (0.85)	88.19 (0.87)

315 **Table 10.** Confusion matrix of the classification obtained for the boosting approach using as predictors
 316 only the six selected Sentinel-2 images, and OSAVI₇₀₅. **Classes: shrubs (SH), fruits (FR), citrus (CI),**
 317 **forest (FO), rice crops (RI), olive grove (OL), pasture with trees (PAT), vineyards (VI), dried fruit**
 318 **(DFR), and pasture (PA).**

Classified	Ground truth										Total	UA (%)
	SH	DFR	FR	PA	RI	FO	VI	PAT	OL	CI		
SH	5050	20	32	2	0	409	2	475	67	9	6066	83.3
DFR	16	6519	9	16	0	27	19	16	72	30	6724	97.0
FR	101	111	6349	17	3	40	70	25	87	40	6843	92.8
PA	3	8	1	6566	0	21	2	4	37	4	6646	98.8
RI	2	3	0	3	6714	2	0	3	2	0	6729	99.8
FO	955	11	17	31	0	5515	1	474	39	14	7057	78.1
VI	13	20	55	2	0	0	6593	8	97	4	6792	97.1
PAT	519	34	51	14	2	689	1	5160	99	11	6580	78.4
OL	129	155	78	32	0	109	62	103	5962	160	6790	87.8
CI	6	20	8	3	0	14	15	14	16	6523	6619	98.5
Total	6794	6901	6600	6686	6719	6826	6765	6282	6478	6795		OA=91.18%
PA (%)	74.3	94.5	96.2	98.2	99.9	80.8	97.5	82.1	92.0	96.0		$\kappa=0.88$

319 For completeness, an experiment taking into account all eleven available Sentinel-2 images in
 320 the training was conducted and revealed worse results (OA=86.21% and $\kappa=0.82$ obtained in the best
 321 case. For the sake of brevity, we show the results in Table S6 of Supplementary Material). This
 322 confirms that the previous Sentinel-2 spectral separability analysis was useful for improving
 323 classification results.
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325 4.3. Classification, class probability, and agreement maps

326 After the accuracy assessment over the test set, the best classifier (i.e., the ensemble of boosting
 327 trees) was executed (using both optical and SAR data as predictors) over the study area to obtain a
 328 classification map (see Figure 5(a)). In addition, the ensemble approach also provides a per pixel
 329 probability of belonging to every class taking into account the predictions of every tree forming the
 330 ensemble of 1000 boosting trees. The per pixel probability of the class with the maximum probability,
 331 which is indeed the predicted class, was used for deriving a map that can be interpreted as the
 332 confidence of the classification (see Figure 5(b)). The 80% of the pixels were classified by a confidence
 333 higher than 50% (see greenish colored areas in Figure 5, right, and cumulative histogram in Figure
 334 6). The 50% of all pixels were classified by a confidence greater than 77% (see Figure 6). The maximum
 335 confidence was achieved over rice pixels (reaching almost 100% of confidence) which jointly with the
 336 spectral analysis undertaken in Section 4.1 corroborates the high reliability in rice classification from
 337 multitemporal Sentinel-1 and -2 data.

338 **Figure 5.** Classification map (a), and associated confidence (b) over the study area.

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 340 **Figure 6.** Cumulative histogram of the confidence map.

341 Taking into account Table 3 described in Section 3.4, we derived the agreement between the
 342 predictions derived from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data, and the SIGPAC (see Figure 7(left)). Most of
 343 the pixels show bluish colors, which indicate the consistency between the classifications performed
 344 in this study and the official land parcel information system of Valencia (see Figure 7(left)). The
 345 highest agreement is found over rice crops whereas significant, high, and very high discrepancies are
 346 found over less than 3.5% of the total classified area over different classes (see Figure 7(left)). In
 347 addition, only 0.1% of the pixels are labeled as very high high discrepancy which highlights the robustness
 348 of the classifier.

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 350 **Figure 7. (Left)** Agreement map showing the level of agreement between classification and SIGPAC
 351 over the study area, **and (right) the corresponding pie chart showing the percentage of pixels for**
 352 **every level of agreement.**

353 *4.4. Utility of the derived agreement map*

354 We provide two examples of the utility of the derived agreement map. The first example is
 355 shown in Figure 8, which displays a zoomed area of the three maps mentioned above containing a
 356 very high discrepancy area (it is highlighted in red, in western part of the displayed maps). It is
 357 classified as forest while the SIGPAC classifies it as citrus. Since the probability of the classification
 358 map over this zone is > 95%, following rules in Table 4, the agreement map assigns to it a very high
 359 discrepancy. If this polygon is superimposed over the official orthophoto of 2017 (provided by
 360 Institut Cartogràfic Valencià) over the zone, it can be observed that the class corresponds to forest
 361 instead of citrus. This means that in this case SIGPAC should be updated.

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Figure 8. Classification (top), SIGPAC (bottom), and agreement (right) over an area identified as very high discrepancy.

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The second example is exhibited in Figure 9, which shows an example of high discrepancy between the derived classification and SIGPAC. The area highlighted in red is classified as fruits while the SIGPAC classifies it as citrus. The agreement map assigns to it a high discrepancy. If this polygon is superimposed over the official orthophoto of 2017 over the zone (Figure 9 (middle)), no conclusion can be drawn and then, a field inspection is recommended to check out the correct class. If the class is identified as citrus, the corresponding pixels should be labeled as citrus and incorporated in future trainings to avoid similar errors. If the field check verifies that the class is fruits, the SIGPAC should be updated

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Figure 9. Classification (top), SIGPAC (bottom), and agreement (right) over an area identified as high discrepancy.

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5. Discussion

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It is recognized that object-based approaches can be useful to delineate polygons over agricultural areas, however their effectiveness for delineating and classifying agricultural parcels using Sentinel-2 time series is reduced [12,45]. In addition, other studies using Sentinel-2 for crop mapping did not found advantages regarding the use of object -based or pixel-based approaches also highlighting the impossibility of using textural features for small objects [9,46]. In this study the classification was carried out at pixel-level since for CAP payments it is relevant not only the classification of and object/polygon, which can be actually done aggregating the result of a pixel-level classification, but also report if over a polygon there exist different classes.

A key aspect in every classification process is related with the training samples selection. The close collaboration with the regional authorities, particularly with its technicians, allowed obtaining a very high number of training samples per class. Our results derived from the JM-BH measures revealed that the highest spectral separabilities among classes were obtained using only six out of the available and cloud-free Sentinel-2 images. The inclusion of the remainder images would decrease accuracy. **This is** mainly due to the non-optimal spectral separability among classes in these dates, and the addition of redundant information, which may introduce noise in the features space of the training samples. This type of feature selection can be useful in order to avoid Hughes phenomenon and improve classification accuracy. **However**, this process must be taken carefully since if not properly addressed relevant information can be lost [20].

395 The classification results reveal the joint use of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and derived vegetation
396 indices improves classification accuracies irrespective of the classification algorithm. Zhong *et al.* [47]
397 recently reported that the use of a single multitemporal vegetation index outperformed the use of
398 only available Landsat reflectances. However, unlike the present study, in their problem the classes
399 were not spectrally separable. It is interesting to note that when stacking the OSAVI versions (i.e.,
400 using either the red (ρ_{665}) or the red-edge band (ρ_{705})) the best results were obtained. This could be
401 partly due to the OSAVI capabilities of minimizing the noise introduced by soil both at sparse and
402 dense vegetation canopies [35]. In addition, the experiments reveal that the use of red-edge not
403 always contributes to improve classification accuracies. OSAVI₇₀₅ seems to capture information
404 provided by the red-edge in the classification process outperforming **slightly** the OSAVI. Conversely,
405 classification accuracy decreases when using NDVI₇₀₅ if compared with cases using NDVI.
406 Furthermore, the results confirmed that the combination of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 leads to
407 improved accuracy in the classification, which highlights the complementary information conveyed
408 by Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2. In particular, our results demonstrate that the inclusion of Sentinel-1
409 data is able to better discriminate classes such as shrubs, forest and pasture with trees that presented
410 rather similar features among them in the optical domain of Sentinel-2.

411 Classification accuracy depends on a number of factors including the number of training and
412 test samples, the number of features and its relevance, the number of classes and its similarity, and
413 the classification algorithm itself. For instance, Schmedtmann & Campagnolo [24] proposed a reliable
414 crop identification (12 classes, OA=68%) over Portuguese parcels covering 1057 km²,
415 Sitokonstantinou *et al.* [25] developed a parcel-based crop identification (9 classes, OA=91.3% and
416 $k=0.87$) scheme for CAP and greening obligations over a Spanish area of 215 km². Kanjir *et al.* [48]
417 developed a change detection method to support land use control within CAP activities over three
418 areas of 7 km² in Slovenia, and Blaes *et al.* [23] developed a framework for area-based subsidies
419 control in Belgium. The present study reported overall accuracy reaching $\approx 94\%$, which is similar to
420 the aforementioned studies. A remarkably high accuracy was found over rice highlighting that its
421 multitemporal features are extremely informative for rice phenology and classification, which is also
422 reported in other studies [47,49-51].

423 The number of available Sentinel-2 images proved to be sufficient for obtaining accurate and
424 satisfactory classification results in most of the classes. This means that the temporal behavior of the
425 majority of classes is captured with as few as six Sentinel-2 multispectral images. However, there was
426 a lack of cloud free Sentinel-2 images during the summer period in 2017 whose data could be of
427 relevance for our study. The inclusion of Sentinel-1 data tried to mitigate this effect and also
428 incorporate information of vegetation structure that is not provided by optical sensors such as the
429 MSI onboard Sentinel-2. Data provided by Sentinel-1 VV and VH polarizations include information
430 on the vegetation status, structure, and their interaction with soil background [52-53]. In addition, the
431 ratio VH/VV can provide time series information on vegetation and soil properties such as soil
432 moisture also reducing SAR acquisition system errors [10,54,55].

433 With the implementation of the new 2020+ CAP regulation, field inspections are earmarked for
434 only 5% of the territory. Therefore, the identification of zones with well-founded suspicions of
435 incompatibility between farmers' declarations and SIGPAC is key. The derived agreement map is
436 intended to help in this process by highlighting agreement and discrepancies between the
437 classification map retrieved with Sentinels data and SIGPAC. Certainly, the definition of the logical
438 rules for deriving the agreement map influences the final result. The rules proposed in Table 4 are
439 fairly reasonable. When some level of discrepancy is found between maps, a photo interpretation
440 using very-high resolution imagery such as orthophotography is recommended. Then if the
441 interpretation tips the scale in favor of the reported classification, SIGPAC should be updated with
442 this class. On the contrary, those pixels should be labeled as SIGPAC does, and could be incorporated
443 into the training process to avoid similar misclassifications in the future. If no conclusion can be
444 drawn a field inspection would be needed. In this study, the agreement map reported less than 3.5%
445 of the pixels as significant, high, and very high discrepancies, hence in the extremely case of
446 impossibility of establish a class by photo interpretation, the number of field visits would fall within

447 the 2020+ CAP regulation allowed range. If the level of discrepancy is low, it is not recommended a
448 field inspection, just photo interpretation, since the confidence of the derived classifications is not
449 very high (< 50% according to the established rules in Table 4) and the classifier may not be
450 performing well over those pixels

451 6. Conclusions

452 A classification framework based on the predictions provided by an ensemble of decision trees
453 using a boosting approach has been developed. Ten classes were classified covering an area of 3568
454 km² which is much bigger than the previous studies dealing with CAP framework. In addition, we
455 also benefit from the per class probability given by the ensemble in order to develop an agreement
456 map between derived classifications and the official LPIS of Spain (SIGPAC).

457 The results revealed an overall accuracy of 93.96% and $\kappa=0.9$ when using both Sentinel-1 and
458 Sentinel-2 data, and the boosting approach in an ensemble of decision trees. The addition of Sentinel-
459 1 to Sentinel-2 data improved classification accuracy with regard to using only Sentinel-2 data. Not
460 only the accuracies were improved in all classes, but also the inter-class confusions were reduced
461 mainly for shrubs, forest and pasture with trees stressing the usefulness of blending Sentinel-1 and
462 Sentinel-2 data. The use of VIs as predictors improved classification accuracies in all cases, being the
463 OSAVI₇₀₅ the VI with which best results were obtained.

464 The derived agreement map reported less than 3.5% of the pixels as significant, high, and very
465 high discrepancies with respect to the classification obtained from Sentinels data. In the case of
466 needing a field inspection for checking the class, the number of field recognitions would fall within
467 the 2020+ CAP regulation allowed range. The agreement map is a clear example of the utility of the
468 proposed methodology and is intended to help in the CAP subsidies payment process. The derivation
469 of this map is a major feature of this work, which is suitable to update Spanish SIGPAC as suggested
470 by the European Court of Auditors also following with the 2020+ CAP regulation.

471 **Supplementary Materials:** The following are available online at www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Table S1: Jeffries–
472 Matusita and Bhattacharyya distances for Sentinel-2 image acquired on June 15, 2017, Table S2: Jeffries–Matusita
473 and Bhattacharyya distances for Sentinel-2 image acquired on October 13, 2017, Table S3: Jeffries–Matusita and
474 Bhattacharyya distances for Sentinel-2 image acquired on December 17, 2017, Table S4: Jeffries–Matusita and
475 Bhattacharyya distances for Sentinel-2 image acquired on January 21, 2018, Table S5: Jeffries–Matusita and
476 Bhattacharyya distances for Sentinel-2 image acquired on March 7, 2018, Table S6: Overall accuracy (OA) and
477 kappa index (κ) obtained in the test set for every classifier using all (eleven) available Sentinel-2 images. Best
478 result highlighted in bold.

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